

EFFICACY OF FACEBOOK AS LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FOR DISTANCE EDUCATION

KEVIN CLIENT B. MATUTES¹, ANNE PAULINE C. PANORIL²,
SARAH LIN A. ROBENTA³

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1313-8087>¹

matuteskcb@gmail.com¹, anneppic96@gmail.com², saralinrobenta7@gmail.com³
School of Teacher Education, Initao College 9022, Initao, Misamis Oriental, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Over the years, Facebook as a social network has improved its features to accommodate the demands of its billions of active users worldwide. The considerable increase of its popularity as the top social media with the greatest number of users today means that many of the world's populations have been using the platform as part of their everyday lives. In absence of an institutional online domain for instructional management procedures during remote learning amid community quarantines caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, this research has taken advantage to the existing fact that 100% of the faculty and students were active users of Facebook as their primary social media platform, and have utilized Facebook as a temporary Learning Management System for Elementary Education Program students of Initao College for S.Y. 2020-2021. It was found out that with the key features of Facebook Page, Group and Messenger as department bulletin, virtual classrooms and main communication platform, the first new normal school year concluded with above average academic achievement and no online learner dropouts for 144 students in total. Furthermore, in terms of average academic performance per year level, ANOVA for independent measures revealed that at $p < 0.05$, there was no significant variation among the average term achievement of the first, second and third year students, $F(2, 284) = 1.00576$, $p\text{-value} = 0.367065$. However, the average achievement of the 144 students of the second semester ($M = 1.72$, $SD = 0.353$) compared to the 143 students during the first semester ($M = 1.46$, $SD = 0.254$) has demonstrated a significantly lower average academic semester achievement, $t\text{-value} = -7.14323$, $p < 0.00001$ at 0.05 significance level. Hence, this decline has been reported for learning management augmentation for S.Y. 2021-2022.

Keywords: Distance Education, COVID-19, Facebook, Learning Management System, Elementary Education Program, Philippines